

COMPARISON OF EFFECTIVENESS OF COMBINATION OF VALSARTAN AND HYDROCHLOROTHIAZIDE VERSUS VALSARTAN ALONE IN THE TREATMENT OF HYPERTENSIVE HEART DISEASE

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Abstract

Background: Hypertensive heart disease causes significant morbidity and mortality. Valsartan effectively manages hypertension, but monotherapy may be insufficient. With limited literature and no local studies, this study evaluated the effectiveness of Valsartan plus Hydrochlorothiazide versus Valsartan alone.

Objectives: To compare combination of valsartan and hydrochlorothiazide versus valsartan alone in the treatment of hypertensive heart disease in terms of effectiveness.

Duration: May 2025 till July 2025

Methodology: A total of 118 patients with hypertensive heart disease were randomly assigned into two groups: Valsartan plus Hydrochlorothiazide or Valsartan alone. Treatment lasted eight weeks, with follow-up for effectiveness and adverse reactions. Data were recorded systematically, ensuring ethical approval, informed consent, and control of confounding variables

Results: In this study of 118 patients, Valsartan combined with Hydrochlorothiazide was more effective than Valsartan alone (91.5% vs 74.6%, $p=0.014$). Subgroup analysis showed higher effectiveness in the combination group across age, gender, BMI, and disease duration, though statistical significance was limited by small sample sizes. Adverse effects were mild, infrequent, and comparable between both treatments.

Conclusion: This study concludes that Valsartan combined with Hydrochlorothiazide is significantly more effective than Valsartan alone in treating hypertensive heart disease, particularly in males and patients with shorter disease duration. Both regimens demonstrated comparable safety profiles, with adverse effects being mild, infrequent, and statistically insignificant, indicating good tolerability of treatments.

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, hypertension remains a growing public health challenge, with the age-standardized prevalence reaching approximately 30% in the general population and up to two-thirds among individuals over 60 years.¹ Between 1990 and 2019, the number of adults aged 30–79 years with hypertension doubled

globally, exceeding one billion cases in 2019.² Projections suggest that the prevalence of hypertension could rise to 1.56 billion by 2025, particularly in rapidly developing countries with limited early screening and preventive strategies. Hypertensive heart disease (HHD) results from prolonged elevated blood pressure, leading to

complex structural and functional cardiac changes, including concentric or eccentric left ventricular hypertrophy and variable ejection fraction, ultimately impairing cardiac function.^{3,4} Hypertension significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular complications such as stroke, myocardial infarction, heart failure, and renal dysfunction.⁵ Accurate diagnosis and classification of HHD are aided by echocardiography and cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (cMRI), which help differentiate HHD from conditions such as hypertrophic cardiomyopathy.⁶ Pharmacologic management remains central to controlling hypertension and preventing target organ damage.⁷ Sacubitril/valsartan, an angiotensin receptor blocker, not only lowers blood pressure but also mitigates left ventricular hypertrophy and improves heart failure outcomes.⁸ Hydrochlorothiazide, a widely used thiazide diuretic, effectively reduces blood pressure, with substantial evidence supporting its efficacy compared to placebo.⁹ Recent study has underscored the benefits of combination therapy: Zhou et al. (2023)¹⁰ reported that Valsartan combined with Hydrochlorothiazide achieved significantly higher effectiveness than Valsartan alone (95.45% vs. 79.63%, $p=0.007$) and was associated with fewer adverse reactions (9.09% vs. 31.48%, $p=0.001$).

METHODOLOGY

This study was designed as a randomized controlled trial conducted in the Department of Cardiology, Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, for three months from May 2025 till July 2025. A total of 118 patients diagnosed with hypertensive heart disease, aged 18–70 years, of both genders, were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling, with 59 patients allocated to each group. The sample size was calculated to achieve 80% power with a 5% level of significance, assuming expected efficacy of 95.4% in the combination group (Valsartan plus Hydrochlorothiazide) and 79.6% in the Valsartan alone group.⁹ Inclusion criteria comprised patients fulfilling the operational definition of hypertensive heart disease, confirmed by sustained systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg, averaged over two readings, and ECG findings consistent with left ventricular hypertrophy using Cornell Voltage Criteria, ST-segment changes, or left atrial enlargement. Exclusion criteria included

patients with drug allergies or contraindications, emergency hypertension cases, poor compliance, concurrent endocrine disorders, coagulation dysfunction, mental disorders, or conditions complicated by infectious or immune diseases. Following ethical approval, informed written consent was obtained, and baseline demographics were recorded. Patients were randomly assigned to Group A, receiving oral Valsartan 80 mg plus Hydrochlorothiazide 25 mg daily for eight weeks, with dose adjustment from 6.5 mg to 13 mg/day according to treatment response, and Group B, receiving Valsartan alone following the same regimen. Treatment effectiveness was assessed at follow-up using the operational definition, categorizing responses as markedly effective, effective, or ineffective, with markedly effective and effective combined as “effective.” Adverse reactions were managed per standard hospital protocol and documented. Data collection and assessment were performed by the resident under supervision of a single senior consultant to minimize bias, and confounding variables were controlled through exclusion criteria. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 26. Numerical variables such as age, BMI, and disease duration were reported as mean \pm SD, while categorical variables including gender, treatment effectiveness, and adverse reactions were expressed as frequency and percentage. Chi-square tests were applied to compare effectiveness and adverse reactions between the groups, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant. Additionally, stratification was performed for age, gender, BMI, and duration of disease to evaluate effect modifiers, followed by post-stratification chi-square analysis to ensure the robustness of the results and to identify any subgroup-specific differences in treatment response and tolerability between the two groups.

RESULTS

A total of 118 patients were enrolled in the study with a mean age of 45.60 ± 12.26 years. Among them, 43 (36.4%) participants were between 18–40 years, while 75 (63.6%) were in the 41–70 year age group. Out of the total, 72 (61.0%) were males and 46 (39.0%) were females. The mean body mass index (BMI) of the study population was 26.85 ± 3.55 kg/m², with 34 (28.8%) participants having a normal weight and 84 (71.2%) classified as overweight or obese. The mean

duration of hypertensive heart disease was 6.66 ± 2.84 years, with 48 (40.7%) patients having the disease for ≤ 5 years and 70 (59.3%) for more than 5 years as given in Table 1.0. Overall, there were no statistically significant differences in baseline demographic or clinical characteristics between the two groups ($p > 0.05$), indicating comparability at the start of the study as given in Table 2.0. Table 3.0 compares the treatment effectiveness between the two study groups. In Group A (Valsartan + Hydrochlorothiazide), 54 patients (91.5%) showed effective treatment response, while only 5 (8.5%) did not respond. In contrast, Group B (Valsartan alone) demonstrated effectiveness in 44 patients (74.6%), whereas 15 (25.4%) showed no response. The difference in treatment effectiveness between the two groups was statistically significant ($p = 0.014$), indicating that the combination therapy of Valsartan and Hydrochlorothiazide was more effective than Valsartan alone in managing

hypertensive heart disease. Subgroup analysis showed consistently higher effectiveness in Group A. Significant differences were found in males (92.1% vs 73.5%, $p = 0.035$) and in disease duration ≤ 5 years (96.0% vs 65.2%, $p = 0.006$). Other subgroup differences favored Group A but remained insignificant, possibly due to smaller sample sizes limiting statistical power. Data is given in Table 4.0. Table 3.0 compares adverse reactions between the two groups. Headache occurred in 11.9% of Group A and 10.2% of Group B, while vertigo was reported in 8.5% and 5.1%, respectively. Nausea was equal in both groups (8.5%), and vomiting was infrequent (6.8% vs 5.1%). Dry cough occurred in 11.9% of Group A and 10.2% of Group B, whereas edema was observed equally (6.8% each). All differences were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$), indicating similar tolerability of both treatments.

Table 1.0: Demographic Characteristics of Patients Undergoing Elective Surgical Procedure

Characteristics	Total (n=118)
Age (years)	45.60±12.26
• 18-40 years	43 (36.4%)
• 41-70 years	75 (63.6%)
Gender	
• Male	72 (61.0%)
• Female	46 (39.0%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.85±3.55
• Normal Weight	34 (28.8%)
• Overweight / Obese	84 (71.2%)
Duration of Disease (years)	6.66±2.84
• ≤ 5 years	48 (40.7%)
• > 5 years	70 (59.3%)

Table 2.0: Comparison of Baseline Characteristics between the Study Groups

Characteristics	Group A (n=59)	Group B (n=59)	p-value
Age (years)	45.20±11.89	46.00±12.71	0.726
• 18-40 years	20 (33.9%)	23 (39.0%)	0.566
• 41-70 years	39 (66.1%)	36 (61.0%)	
Gender			
• Male	38 (64.4%)	34 (57.6%)	0.450
• Female	21 (35.6%)	25 (42.4%)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.58±3.40	27.11±3.69	0.422
• Normal Weight	19 (32.2%)	15 (25.4%)	0.416

• Overweight / Obese	40 (67.8%)	44 (74.6%)	
Duration of Disease (years)	6.59±2.93	6.73±2.77	0.797
• ≤5 years	25 (42.4%)	23 (39.0%)	0.708
• >5 years	34 (57.6%)	36 (61.0%)	

Chi Square test/ Independent sample t test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

Table 3.0: Comparison of Effectiveness of Treatment between the Groups

Effectiveness	Group A (n=59)	Group B (n=59)	p-value
Yes	54 (91.5%)	44 (74.6%)	0.014
No	5 (8.5%)	15 (25.4%)	

Chi Square test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

Table 4 .0: Stratification of Effectiveness of Treatment between the Groups for Various Sub Groups.

Characteristics	Group A (59)	Group B (n=59)	p-value
Age (years)			
• 18-40 years	18/20 (90.0%)	17/23 (73.9%)	0.076
• 41-70 years	36/39 (92.3%)	27/36 (75.0%)	0.059
Gender			
• Male	35/38 (92.1%)	25/34 (73.5%)	0.035
• Female	19/21 (90.5%)	19/25 (76.0%)	0.197
BMI (kg/m²)			
• Normal Weight	18/19 (94.7%)	12/15 (80.0%)	0.185
• Overweight / Obese	36/40 (90.0%)	32/44 (72.7%)	0.055
Duration of Disease (years)			
• ≤5 years	24/25 (96.0%)	15/23 (65.2%)	0.006
• >5 years	30/34 (88.2%)	29/36 (80.6%)	0.378

Chi Square test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

Table 5.0: Comparison of Adviser Reactions between the Groups

Characteristics	Group A (59)	Group B (n=59)	p-value
Headache			
• Yes	7 (11.9%)	6 (10.2%)	0.769
• No	52 (88.1%)	53 (89.8%)	
Vertigo			
• Yes	5 (8.5%)	3 (5.1%)	0.717
• No	54 (91.5%)	56 (94.9%)	
Nausea			
• Yes	5 (8.5%)	5 (8.5%)	1.000
• No	54 (91.5%)	54 (91.5%)	
Vomiting			
• Yes	4 (6.8%)	3 (5.1%)	1.000
• No	55 (93.2%)	56 (94.9%)	
Dry Cough			
• Yes	7 (11.9%)	6 (10.2%)	0.769
• No	52 (88.1%)	53 (89.8%)	

Odema			
• Yes	4 (6.8%)	4 (6.8%)	1.000
• No	55 (93.2%)	55 (93.2%)	

Chi Square test/Fisher’s Exact test, taking p-value≤0.05 as significant.

DISCUSSION

Hypertensive heart disease is a major global health concern, contributing to significant morbidity and mortality due to sustained elevated blood pressure and its cardiovascular complications.¹¹⁻¹² Valsartan, an angiotensin receptor blocker, is widely used to manage hypertension and reduce cardiac strain. However, monotherapy may not always achieve optimal blood pressure control, necessitating combination therapy.¹³ Hydrochlorothiazide, a thiazide diuretic, is often added to enhance antihypertensive efficacy.¹³ Scarce literature exists comparing the combination versus Valsartan alone, and no local studies have addressed this issue. Therefore, this study was planned to evaluate the effectiveness and tolerability of Valsartan plus Hydrochlorothiazide compared to Valsartan monotherapy in patients with hypertensive heart disease.

In this study, total of 118 patients were enrolled with a mean age of 45.60 ± 12.26 years; 36.4% were between 18–40 years, while 63.6% were aged 41–70 years. The cohort included 61.0% males and 39.0% females, with a mean BMI of 26.85 ± 3.55 kg/m². Most patients (71.2%) were overweight or obese, and the mean disease duration was 6.66 ± 2.84 years. Baseline characteristics were comparable between groups (p>0.05). Valsartan with Hydrochlorothiazide showed higher effectiveness (91.5% vs 74.6%, p=0.014), especially in males and those with shorter disease duration. Adverse reactions, including headache, vertigo, nausea, vomiting, dry cough, and edema, were mild, infrequent, and comparable between groups.

Evidence from international studies supports the superiority of combination therapy. Ruvolve et al. in Turkey demonstrated that full-dose Valsartan plus hydrochlorothiazide achieved optimal blood pressure control and regression of target organ damage within three months, without significant adverse effects.¹⁵ Similarly, Zappe et al. in China reported that initiating therapy with Valsartan combined with low-dose hydrochlorothiazide led to early and improved

blood pressure reduction with tolerability comparable to Valsartan monotherapy.¹⁶ Zhou et al., also in China, observed that combination therapy was significantly more effective than Valsartan alone (95.45% vs. 79.63%; p=0.007), while total adverse reactions were notably lower in the combination group (9.09% vs. 31.48%; p=0.001).¹⁰ Chazova et al. concluded that valsartan, whether used alone or in fixed-dose combination with hydrochlorothiazide, effectively reduced systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Ninety-one percent (91%) of patients achieved target levels, while tolerability remained favorable, with only mild adverse reactions such as headache, dizziness, and fatigue reported infrequently during treatment.¹⁷

Comparative studies in Pakistan, such as Dar et al., also support the enhanced efficacy and safety of Valsartan plus hydrochlorothiazide over other combinations like Valsartan plus Amlodipine, with higher response rates (80% vs. 72%) and fewer side effects.¹⁸ Marfatia et al. in the USA similarly reported effective blood pressure goal achievement and good tolerability with combination therapy.¹⁹

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that Valsartan combined with Hydrochlorothiazide is significantly more effective than Valsartan alone in treating hypertensive heart disease, particularly in males and patients with shorter disease duration. Both regimens demonstrated comparable safety profiles, with adverse effects being mild, infrequent, and statistically insignificant, indicating good tolerability of treatments.

LIMITATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The study’s strengths include a clearly defined patient population, balanced baseline characteristics, and comprehensive evaluation of both effectiveness and safety of Valsartan plus Hydrochlorothiazide. Limitations involve a relatively small sample size, short follow-up duration, and single-center design, which may limit generalizability. Future research

should involve larger, multicenter trials with extended follow-up to assess long-term cardiovascular outcomes, sustained blood pressure control, and rare adverse events, providing stronger evidence for combination therapy in hypertensive heart disease management.

Conflict of Interest: None

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